

Applied AI and Federated Learning in HPC: *Because Even Supercomputers Need a Team*

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Abstract—The High-Performance Computing (HPC) paradigm, which forms the backbone of global cloud infrastructure, has experienced exponential growth through multiple iterations. Initially used for scientific computing, later for productivity, and more recently Artificial Intelligence (AI) based services, this application growth has further contributed to the complexity of the HPC hardware-software ecosystem, creating new challenges and opportunities in the domain. Given the innate nature of computing is highly distributed, tiered, and evolving, several decisions must be made locally across non-overlapping decision boundaries often with multiple local and global objectives for optimization. Such optimization goals span energy, cost, performance, and environmental impact. In this paper, we present our most recent works in the applications of AI for HPC, with a special focus on applications in federated digital twins, intelligent storage buffer cache, application performance projection, and energy-aware scheduling.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, HPC, Applied AI, Digital Twins, Cloud, Storage.

I. INTRODUCTION

With rapid advancements in digital technologies, an incomprehensible amount of data is created everyday from various sources such as social media, video streaming, IoT devices etc. The amount of data generated is projected to reach around 175 zettabytes (175 trillion gigabytes) by 2025 [1]. A significant portion of this data is expected to be stored in the cloud, with high-performance computing (HPC) playing a critical role due to its immense computational potential and scalability. Additionally, a good portion of the generated data will require advanced analytics to analyze and deliver beneficial insights [2]. AI is a powerful tool for data analysis beyond basic queries and hypotheses. It also aids in exploring trends and making predictions to leverage explicit knowledge into decision-making.

Although distinct computing technologies, HPC and AI are evolving to become complementary given the benefits the fields offer to each other. For instance, training machine learning (ML) models requires processing of diverse voluminous data, and HPC provides the vast amount of computational power necessary to handle these large datasets efficiently or run simulations. Moreover, the parallel nature of most deep learning algorithms aligns well with the parallel processing over multiple processors in HPC, leading to optimized resource utilization. On the other hand, AI can automate and optimize complex workflows and job submissions, which can significantly reduce the manual overhead to improve

the efficiency of HPC tasks. AI can also provide advanced simulation and modelling capabilities by learning from past data to increase the simulation accuracy and speed.

Employing centralized ML algorithms in this context proves to be rather inefficient due to the substantial communication and storage requirements that arise from uploading and storing large volumes of the generated private data from numerous devices [3]. Additionally, frequently fragmented across various organizations as data silos [4], it is often not practical to consolidate these data into large datasets due to stringent privacy regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [5] in Europe, the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) [6] in the United States. Hence, a relatively recent distributed computing paradigm that can be used to address these issues is federated learning (FL) [7].

FL is a distributed ML technique consisting of multiple decentralized devices that collaboratively train a shared model by exchanging local updates, rather than raw data; thus enhancing privacy and compliance, which is crucial in sensitive fields like healthcare. FL can further leverage the scalability provided by HPC to process the distributed model training over massive local datasets privately which can offer enhanced performance possibilities and further advance applications such as autonomous driving [8], smart cities [9], finance, etc.

II. FEDERATED LEARNING AS APPLIED AI

Applying FL for scalable and efficient collaborative training, its global objective of minimizing the global loss is given by,

$$\min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d} F(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{D_n}{D} f_n(\mathbf{w}), \quad (1)$$

where D_n is the size of the local dataset of the participant device n and $D = \sum_{n=1}^N D_n$ is the total data size of N devices. The device's local objective with loss function l is,

$$f_n(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{D_n} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}_n} l(x_i^n, y_i^n; \mathbf{w}). \quad (2)$$

Although initially proposed for next word prediction application on smart phones, leveraging its feature of working with heterogeneous data on heterogeneous systems, FL has come a long way to being a critical learning paradigm in massive industries where data privacy is of utmost importance. Below, we introduce a list of four of our recent and original works that implement applied AI and/or FL in the context of HPC.

III. APPLICATIONS, USE CASES AND IMPACT

A. Federated Digital Twins for Datacenters

Fig. 1. Federated Digital Twin architecture

Reliable and uninterrupted operation in datacenters (supercomputers) is vital, especially for handling anomalies. Additionally, relying on a single system is not feasible during outages or failures; a failover mechanism is essential to ensure continuous operation. Hence, in the stated work, we propose a federated approach where multiple data centers are monitored and managed through individual digital twins working in federation as shown in Fig. 1. The trained model predicts system utilization values in order to detect anomalies and raise appropriate alarms to get the attention of the system maintainer/administrator as demonstrated in Fig. 2. FL’s decentralized approach facilitates the development of a hierarchy of multi-level models across these data centers by using the data generated and stored locally, thereby reducing data transfer and enhancing security while still delivering robust monitoring and predictive services. Overall, we leverage the adaptability and versatility of Gaussian Process Regression models [10] to integrate insights (and not data) from various data centers, enhancing the overall management and monitoring.

B. Storage Buffer Cache

As distributed modern storage architectures entail nodes with layered buffer caches, each utilizing different eviction strategies to optimize for different objectives, the primary goal is to reduce the host-perceived latency of requests. FL improves the buffer cache management without compromising the privacy of the data, and even improving the latency of requests. Specifically, it helps in understanding the patterns of requests in distributed nodes, as well as their seasonality, to offer the best possible performance at a minimal cost.

C. Application Performance Prediction

In modern computing environments, users often face the challenge of selecting the best system and configuration for their applications due to the variety of options available. We propose an AI-powered prediction tool that forecasts the performance-cost trade-offs of an application across multiple systems by profiling a limited number of configurations and

Fig. 2. Adaptive anomaly detection by the digital twin. (a) Anomaly injected at 15:25 leads to increased detection frequency and subsequent alarms. (b) high error at 14:26 prompts a temporary frequency increase, reverting after error absence.

using that data to estimate performance for all configurations. This tool automates configuration selection, offers predictions with minimal online profiling, and provides insights without requiring to run the application extensively [11].

D. Energy-Aware Scheduling

While HPC systems provide the computational power and resources needed for running large models like LLMs, energy and sustainability remains a concern. While this problem can be partly mitigated by the compression of the individual workloads themselves (such as quantization of large deep learning models) [12], [13], it is not sufficient to optimize the workload alone.

Data center workloads vary significantly, peaking during the day and dropping at night. Despite this, servers often stay on continuously, leading to higher energy costs, increased carbon emissions, and inefficient utilization. Hence, we propose a demand-aware cluster resizing approach that adjusts server activity on an ML-based solution that predicts the server loads and proactively manages server power.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we first present the application of FL for data-center digital twins. In this work, we implement a framework for monitoring, predictive maintenance and detecting anomalies. Further, we also chose to enable federated intelligence in the design of storage buffer caches. Our federated approach learns and adapts to the pattern of requests and seasonality across distributed buffer cache nodes. This was followed by our framework for performance prediction and rightsizing, which allows us to evaluate the performance and cost trade-off in the allocation of HPC resources. Finally, we discuss our data-driven energy-aware AI scheduler for data center workloads. By focusing on these key areas, we illustrate how AI-driven solutions can address critical optimization objectives such as energy efficiency, cost management, and performance improvement. Through the work presented in this paper, we underscore the importance of delivering modular solutions that can be easily integrated into disaggregated HPC systems. As HPC continues to evolve, the insights and methods discussed here will be crucial in guiding the development of more efficient, scalable, and intelligent computing systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to thank my team at Hewlett Packard Labs, Dejan Milojevic, Ebad Taheri, Pedro Bruel, Gourav Rattihalli, Ninad Hogade, Eitan Frachtenberg, Aditya Dhakal, Rolando Pablo Hong Enriquez for their support and contributions.

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